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**Pilot Study on Early Signs, Symptoms and Nutritional Parameters among
Head and Neck Cancer: A Prospective Study in Varanasi**

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ABSTRACT

Head and Neck (H&N) cancer is the most common cancer identified among men in India, with an increased global burden. A strong association has been observed with the presence of extraneous variables, such as alcohol intake, tobacco consumption, undernutrition, and exposure to ultraviolet rays. The study aims to assess the early signs of clinical symptoms and nutritional status of head and neck cancer patients. The prospective study design was conducted in the Department of Radiotherapy and Radiation Medicine, Sir Sunder Lal Hospital, BHU Varanasi. A purposive sampling technique was used to obtain data from the patients attending OPD with the help of self-structured questionnaire in regard to social demographic profile, material habits, nutritional status and clinical signs and symptoms of the treatment of head and neck cancer. Twenty patients were selected in the study which were adult individuals diagnosed with H&N cancer and were referred for radiation with or without chemotherapy treatment. The average age of the subject was between 50 to 60 years with maximum reported cases of oral cancers followed by oropharynx and larynx. Presence of deleterious habits including tobacco, cigarette, alcohol, and betel quid (paan) in all subjects prior to the diagnosis of H&N cancer. All subjects had low-calorie, protein, carbohydrate, and fat content with 20% of cases reported to be underweight prior to treatment. A higher significant association was found across cancer type and clinical symptoms in terms of persistent sore, dryness in the mouth, growth of lumps and thickness of skin, change in voice, difficulty in eating, and swelling, with the least significant association in change of taste. The prevalence of Head and neck cancer cases is increasing at an alarming rate. However, a lack of awareness towards clinical symptoms and nutritional intervention therapy exacerbates the situation. Further, upcoming researches should focus on developing modified therapeutic diets and health supplements for preventing post-treatment complications.

Keywords: Head and neck cancer, clinical symptoms, Nutritional status, deleterious habits, oral cancer

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Introduction

Head and neck (H&N) cancers are primary malignant neoplasms that arise in various anatomical sites such as oral cavity, scalp, ear, nasal cavities, nasopharynx, paranasal sinuses, hypopharynx, larynx, and salivary glands¹. It is characterized by loco regional disease with a tendency for metastasis to the cervical lymph nodes. The surgical identification of lymph node metastases is crucial for the effective treatment of H&N Cancer patients². The prevalence of H&N cancer in accord with the total body malignancy varies from 9.8% to 40%. In India, the rate of incidences of cancer increases day by day. According to GLOBOCAN 2020, by 2040 India will be witnessing 2.1 million new cancer cases with an increase of 57.5% from 2020. ³ Head & Neck cancer

cases account for 30% of all-form of reported cases⁴. Further, in India population-based cancer registries (PBCRs) show that the male population from Delhi, Aurangabad, Chennai, and Bhopal; and females of Nagpur are prone to H&N cancer⁵. The appearance of clinical signs of H&N cancer depends on the site of origin of the tumour and the stage of the disease. In the early stages, the signs and symptoms are usually ambiguous. The H&N region may present severe pain, massive lymphadenopathy (abnormal size of lymph nodes), airway obstruction, dysphagia (swallowing difficulty), trismus (restricted opening of the mouth), diplopia (double vision) and neuropathies (nerve damage)⁶. Shunyu *et al.*, (2013)⁷ reported a strong association of H&N cancer with certain confounding variables, i.e., alcohol, tobacco, poor nutrition, and exposure to ultraviolet rays. Acharya *et al.*, (2021)⁸ study also reports a strong association with premalignant lesions (oral cancer) and tobacco chewing, combined bidi and cigarette, and alcohol consumption. Tobacco intake either smoking or smokeless (chewing) are most harmful and is a major cause of oral cancer.

Cancer cachexia or a complex syndrome associated with involuntary weight loss and underlying sickness. Unintentional weight loss over 6-month period up to 5% is often linked with longer hospitalisation, severe toxicities and short survival time among cachexia patients⁹. Weight loss is attributed to two main factors: an increase in energy expenditure and a decrease in dietary intake¹⁰. Normal dietary intake is typically influenced by social, psychological and physiological stimuli. However, the hypothalamus's inability to regulate appetite is attributed to be the major cause of cancer-related reductions in the dietary intake level¹¹. Cancer patients report a variety of symptoms known as nutrition impact symptoms which constitute a barrier to their dietary intake including, nausea, vomiting, dysgeusia, diarrhoea, constipation, depression, anxiety and pain. Although there is limited information about how each nutrition impact symptoms especially contribute to reduced dietary intake levels^{10,12,13}. Vissink *et al.*, (2003)¹⁴ reported H&N cancer patients are more susceptible to nutritionally vulnerable group due to mouth sores, dysphagia, xerostomia, dental issues, and trouble chewing are nutrition-impacted symptoms frequently associated to cancer sites and reduced dietary intake. Additionally, nutritional complications are often imposed by the subsequent treatment of H&N cancer in stage 1 or in stage 2 with definitive radiotherapy (RT) alone, or in combination with more advanced cancers with RT in conjugation with surgery and chemotherapy¹⁴. However, previous studies have suggested nutrition intervention plays an important role in preventing malnutrition and treatment-related weight loss. Oral nutritional support is the first-line defence mechanisms in preventing additional nutritional decline and address current needs, only if oral routes are not contraindicated¹⁵. Moreover, research suggests that in head and neck cancer patients, dysphagia can appear before any oncological treatment (secondary to the basic disease) and during or after oncological treatment (surgery, chemoradio therapy) as the result of the treatment toxicity. As a result, early nutritional assistance is necessary. However, there is limited information about the relationship between nutrition impact symptoms, reduced dietary intake or weight loss.

Therefore, the present study aims to assess the early signs of clinical manifestation and nutritional status of H&N cancer in relation to socio-demographic profile, presence of deleterious habits, nutritional status and clinical signs during the time of diagnosis.

Methodology

The prospective study design was conducted in the Department of Radiotherapy and Radiation Medicine, Sir Sunder Lal Hospital, BHU, Varanasi. A purposive sampling technique was used to collect the data from the patients attending O.P.D. A total of 20 patients were selected in the study which were adult individuals diagnosed with H&N cancer and were referred for treatment (radiation with or without chemotherapy /or surgery) according to the standard protocol depending on the stage, location, and general health. A self-structured questionnaire was used to collect information regarding socio-demographic profile, presence of deleterious habits, nutritional status via the 24-hour recall method, and clinical manifestation prior to the treatment of H&N cancer cases. All the data was collected prior to chemo/radiotherapy and all the participants were on 100% oral intake at the time of study, and no patient used any form of tube feeding (enteral or total parenteral nutrition). Informed consents were obtained from all patients and airborne precautions were used during the time of data collection. All the obtained data was analysed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 16 (IBM Corp., Armonk, USA). Continuous and categorical variables were expressed in frequencies and percentages. A two-sided alpha was considered significant p-value less than 0.005. Categorical groups were compared by chi-square (χ^2) test.

Results and Discussion

The H&N neck cancer is the most common cancer in males in India. The current study is a single hospital-based prospective study to investigate the association of early signs of clinical manifestation and incidence of H&N cancer in terms of socio-demographic characteristics, presence of deleterious habits, nutritional status, and clinical signs during the time of diagnosis.

Socio-demographic Profile: Table-1 represents the socio-demographic characteristics of H&N cancer patients. On the basis of age distribution, it was found that the major number of subjects belonged to 50-60 (40%) and 40-50years (30%), followed by 30-40 years (15%), >60 years (10%) and only 5% were aged less than 30 years. All the subjects were reported to be male (100%). Major subjects belong to the rural population (75%) whereas a lesser number of subjects belong to the urban population (25%). According to the educational status, it was found that 50% of the participants had completed their secondary education, followed by 30%, and 5% had obtained primary education and graduation degrees, however, 15% of them were illiterate. Further, a maximum number of subjects were relying on farming and agriculture professions (50%), followed by 20% indulged in automobiles, 10% in business, 5% in private companies, and 15% were jobless. The socioeconomic status of the subjects shows 85% belonging to the lower-income group and 15% belonging to the middle-income group.

The present study observed that the average age was between 50-60 years with all reported cases to be male subjects. Singh *et al.*, (2016)¹⁶ reported the incidence of H&N cancer is twice as common in men compared to women and with the highest reported cases being between 50-59 years (Aggarwal *et al.*, 2015)¹⁷ which shows that male patients are more affected by H&N cancer.

Table -1: Socio-demographic profile of Head and Neck Cancer patients

Variables	%	
Age group	<30 years	5
	30-40 years	15
	40-50 years	30
	50-60 years	40
	>60 years	10
Gender	Male	100
Residence	Rural	75
	Urban	25
Educational status	Primary	30
	Secondary	50
	Graduate	5
	Illiterate	15
Occupational status	Private job	5
	Business	10
	Farmer	50
	Automobile	20
	Jobless	15
Socio-economic status	Middle	15
	Lower	85

Prevalence of Head and Neck cancer: Based on the prevalence of H&N cancer, oral cancer was found to be the predominant in H&N cancer followed by oropharynx and larynx cancer (**Figure 1**). The present study reports 70% cases of oral cancer, and 15% each case of pharynx and larynx cancer, respectively, which was consistent with other literature based on H&N cancer which showed cases of 22.9% pharynx and 19.1% larynx cancer, yet oral cancer found contrary result (31.7%)¹⁸.

Deleterious Habits

When subjects were inquired about the consumption of deleterious substances it was observed that major subjects were eating paan (70%), consuming tobacco (60%), taking alcohol (50%) and smoking cigarettes (40%) on a regular basis prior to the diagnosis of the H& N cancer (Table 2). In India, major risk factors may vary from different cultures and socioeconomic groups.

Figure-1: Prevalence of Head and neck cancer in patients

However, risks for the development of oral cancer include smokeless tobacco and oral snuff, the chewing of betel quid (paan), alcohol intake and oral potentially malignant disorders^{19,18}. This study also reported all subjects irrespective of their age were eating paan, smokeless tobacco, alcohol and smoking cigarettes on a regular basis prior to the diagnosis of the cancer. Other contributory factors include deficiency of macro and micronutrients (Vitamin A, C, E and iron) and influences of human papillomavirus (HPV). Additionally, a strong association has been observed between educational status and oral health outcomes. Less educational accomplishment is often linked with various deleterious habits²⁰. A study reported by Kumar *et al.*, (2014)²¹ reports adolescents with low educational status are more likely to engage in unhealthy eating practices such as smoking, excess alcohol intake, poor dietary habits and low physical activity. These behaviours can further lead to various health issues such as obesity, diabetes, heart disease, and certain types of cancer. Therefore, education plays a crucial role in shaping an individual’s health behaviours and reduction in deleterious habits.

Table-2: Presence of deleterious habits among respondents

Variables	Present	Absent
	%	%
Tobacco	60	40
Smoking cigarette	40	60
Eating paan	70	30
Alcohol intake	50	50

Clinical Signs and Symptoms: Based on the early signs of head and neck cancer cases, it was found that major subjects experience difficulty in eating, swallowing (dysphagia), change in voice, persistent sore, growth of lumps/ thickening of skin, change in taste, dryness in mouth, sore throat, breathing difficulty, tongue or jaw pain, headache, trouble hearing, red or white patches, loosening of teeth, sore that bleed, and blood in coughing, respectively (**Figure 2**).

Figure-2: Prevalence of clinical signs and symptoms in Head and Neck cancer subjects

Nutritional Status of Head and Neck Cancer Patients

When evaluating the nutritional status of H&N cancer subjects it was observed that 80% of the subjects fall under normal BMI and 20% fall underweight. On the basis of the 24-hour recall method, it was estimated that 100% of the subjects were consuming a low-calorie diet, followed by 90% and 65% each were taking a low protein diet, low fat and carbohydrate diet, respectively. Also, 10% and 20% each were taking normal protein, fat and carbohydrate diet, respectively. Further, 3% each were taking high fat and carbohydrate diet (Table 3).

Table-3: Nutritional status of H&N cancer patients

Variables		Prevalence (%)
Body Mass Index (BMI)	Underweight (<18.5)	20
	Normal (18.5-25.5)	80
Energy	Low	100
	Normal	0
	High	0
Protein	Low	90
	Normal	10
	High	0
Fat	Low	65
	Normal	20
	High	15
Carbohydrate	Low	65
	Normal	20
	High	15

Both malnutrition and weight loss have been linked as a prognostic factor for H&N cancer. Poor state of nutrition has been shown to increase the risk of mortality than tumour-node metastasis stage²². There is independent evidence associated with prior and post-radiation therapy weight loss and increase incidence of death among cancer patient²³. However, improving a patient's nutritional status reverses this trend and increases survival^{23,24}. The current study suggests that 100% of the patients were subjected to low calories, and 90% and 65% each had low protein, fat and carbohydrate, respectively, which lead to a major independent variable responsible for the development of H&N cancer. The majority of the population (75%) comes from the rural community which affects both the quality and quantity of food intake and dietary profile. In addition, the BMI of the patients was found to be normal for 80% of patients and 20% were underweight which reflects the pre-treatment body weight of a patient must be framed against further losses expected during treatment. Radiotherapy alone may cause 5% loss in body weight, however with paired with other adjuvant treatments increases up to the range of 15 to 20% body weight loss²⁵. There is a significant risk associated with pre- and post-treatment weight losses, although larger body weight is advantageous as a higher body mass index (BMI) are significantly associated with long-term survival in H&N cancer patients²⁶, though the findings were inconsistent with the present study.

Association of clinical symptoms and head and Neck Cancer: Table 4 shows the association of clinical symptoms and H&N cancer cases, it was observed that a highly significant association was observed between persistent sore (p=0.001), dryness in mouth (p=0.002), growth of lumps and thickness of skin (p=0.002), change in voice (p=0.001), difficulty in eating (p=0.001) and swallowing (p=0.001), though least significance was observed in the change in taste (p=0.005) in respect to H&N cancer cases. However, no significant difference was observed in blood in coughing (p=0.469), soreness that bleeds (p=0.240), headache (p=0.099), loosening to the tooth (p=0.240), tongue pain or jaw stiffness (p=0.009), breathing problem (p=0.009), Trouble in hearing (p=0.159), Sore throat (p=0.030), and red or white patches (p=0.159). The association of clinical symptoms with H&N cancer cases has been extensively studied. Schmidt *et al.*, (2013) study based on a Head and Neck patient's symptom checklist suggests the prevalence of pain and other symptoms in patients, Siddiqui *et al.*, (2008)²⁷ reported poorer quality of life (QOL), poor functioning, and severe symptoms from pre-to-post-treatment in H&N cancer patients with no distant secondary malignant growth, and Shepherd *et al.*(2004)²⁸ reported change in symptoms from 3 months after treatment in patients with oral or

oropharyngeal cancer. According to Hanna *et al.*, (2015)²⁹ more than 1/3rd of pre-treatment patients is affected with moderated to severe disease-specific symptoms and may required curative management at the time of treatment initiation. As the treatment will progress, it is normal to anticipate that their symptoms would get worsen.

Table-4: Association of Clinical symptoms with Head and Neck Cancer cases

Clinical symptoms	HN Cancer N=20	χ^2	P-value
Blood in coughing	3	1.5	0.469
Persistent sore	13	15.9	<0.001**
Sore that bleed	5	2.8	0.240
Headache	7	4.6	0.099
Loosening to tooth	5	2.8	0.240
Tongue pain or jaw stiffness	7	4.6	0.009
Breathing problem	7	4.6	0.009
Trouble in hearing	6	3.6	0.159
Sore throat	9	7.01	0.030
Red or white patches	6	3.6	0.159
Dryness in mouth	12	12.8	0.002**
Change in taste	11	10.4	0.005*
Lumps and thickness	12	12.8	0.002**
Change in voice	13	15.9	<0.001**
Difficulty in eating	14	16.4	<0.001**
Difficulty in swallowing	13	15.9	<0.001**
*Least significant association, **Highly significant association			

The present study also shows significant association between the presence of clinical symptoms and other variables with H&N cancer with persistent soreness, dryness in the mouth, growth of lumps and thickness of skin, change in voice, and difficulty in eating and swallowing. Though dysphagia is regarded as the leading factor behind reduced food intake and weight loss, however the findings indicate there are other nutrition-impacted symptoms as well (such as pain, anorexia, mouth sores and others) which are independently associated with reduced dietary intake or weight loss and diminished functional capacity.

Association of Nutritional Status and Clinical Symptoms: Table 5 shows no correlation between nutritional status and clinical symptoms including dryness in mouth (0.06), difficulty in eating (p=0.19), and difficulty in swallowing (p=0.10). The present study could not find any significant difference between nutritional status and clinical symptoms as the study was limited to the pre-clinical assessment and did not include post-treatment modalities. Most of the patients report struggling with appetite, weight loss, swallowing, sore throat, taste alteration, and xerostomia. Dryness in the mouth is experienced in the early stage, and patients complain of unfamiliar and unpleasant sensations, feeling as if they had cotton inside their mouth and their tongue stuck to the palate³⁰. After the first 2-3 weeks of radiotherapy, nutritional symptoms like thick saliva and dysphagia (difficulty in swallowing), became very painful and resulted in reduced ability to eat³¹. The increased quantity of saliva with more viscousness, needed saliva to be swallowed actively, resulting in difficulty in chewing and swallowing of food and an increased sense of nausea³⁰. Furthermore, some patients reported severe symptoms of dryness, swelling, narrowness, and pain in mouth and throat which resulted in constant weight loss and made impossible for them to take frequent dietary intake.

Table-5: Association of nutritional status with clinical symptoms of H&N cancer patients

Nutritional Status		Clinical Symptoms					
BMI		Dryness in mouth (N=20)		Difficulty in eating		Difficulty in swallowing	
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Underweight	Yes	4	100.0	4	100.0	4	100.0
	No	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Normal	Yes	8	50.0	11	68.8	9	56.2
	No	8	50.0	5	31.2	7	43.8
Chi square (χ^2)		3.33		1.66		2.69	
P-value		0.06		0.19		0.10	
<i>Mean significance was considered at 0.05 level</i>							

Limitation: The current study includes a relatively small sample size, short duration of time and only confined to pre-assessment study which may restrict the generalizability of the findings to the broader population. Additionally, the study was confined to a single-hospital care unit, potentially limiting the comprehensive understanding of the phenomena under investigation.

Conclusion

In India, the prevalence of cancer is increasing at an alarming rate. Head and neck cancer are primarily malignant neoplasms that emerge out of various anatomical sites. Some of the extraneous variables such as alcohol, tobacco (smoking and smokeless), cigarettes, poor nutrition, exposure to ultraviolet rays, and HPV infection are strongly associated with causing malignant lesions. Further, pre/post-treatment with radiotherapy, chemotherapy or surgery affects nutrition-impacted symptoms (nausea, vomiting, dysgeusia, diarrhoea, depression, anxiety, etc.) and constitutes a barrier with dietary intake ultimately resulting in excessive weight loss. Therefore, nutritional intervention plays a significant role in the management of H&N cancer and its associated treatment modalities. Nutrition intervention including relaxation from previous therapeutic diets to minimize further macro and micro-nutrient deficiencies and to positively influence quality of life outcomes. Traditional food fortification, bio-fortification and oral nutritional support (complete liquid supplements) can be initiated at any point from diagnosis to correct pre-existing nutritional deficiency with regular reviews throughout each stage of treatment in order to optimize nutritional status. Further, future research should focus on developing improved and modified therapeutic diets and health supplements for preventing post-treatment complications.

Conflict of Interest: The author declared no conflict of interest.

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